

Challenges of Governance and Democracy in Nepal: Struggling to Achieve Stability and Development

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Abstract: Despite Nepal's seven decades of democratic practice, the country remains trapped in underdevelopment and backwardness. The governance and democracy of Nepal are presently grappling with a myriad of challenges that have a significant impact on the nation's political, socio-economic progress, and overall prosperity. This study aims to analyze and elucidate these obstacles facing governance and democracy, offering suggestions for overcoming them. Utilizing a qualitative analysis methodology that includes a thorough review of pertinent literature, examination of official documents, and a comparative assessment of critical issues, this paper presents valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders. Key hindrances such as political instability, weak institutional frameworks, slow economic growth, and insufficient citizen participation are identified for in-depth scrutiny. Strategic recommendations are proposed to strengthen democratic processes, improve governance efficiency, and drive socio-economic advancement in Nepal. By enriching comprehension of governance and democracy in Nepal, this study advocates for the adoption of good governance principles and the bolstering of democratic norms to foster sustainable development, enhance prosperity, and elevate governance effectiveness overall.

Key Words: Democracy, governance, political instability, socio-economic development.

1. Introduction: The concepts of governance and democracy are intricately connected and have a profound impact on how a society operates and the quality of life of its people. Democracy, as a political system, is characterized by several key principles such as popular sovereignty, the rule of law, political equality, political pluralism, individual rights and freedoms, transparency, accountability, and the presence of free and fair elections. (Curato, 2021) These pillars of democracy ensure that power is vested in the hands of the people, laws are applied equally to all, citizens have equal opportunities to participate in political processes, diverse perspectives are respected, individual liberties are protected, governmental actions are open to public scrutiny, and elections are conducted in a transparent and impartial manner. On the other hand, governance encompasses the multifaceted processes involved in how a country is controlled, including the various approaches to governing, decision-making mechanisms, and the implementation of policies within the framework of a political system.

In a democratic setting, governance embodies key democratic principles such as representation, accountability, transparency, adherence to the rule of law, responsiveness to citizen needs, and involvement in decision-making processes. Democracy forms the basis for

governance to operate, while effective governance systems enhance and uphold democratic values. This synergy creates a resilient and inclusive political landscape that protects the rights and interests of all citizens. Essentially, democracy underpins governance, and good governance bolsters democracy, leading to a strengthened and participatory societal framework.

Nepal's journey towards democracy and governance has been turbulent over the decades. The country has faced significant challenges in maintaining government stability and upholding democratic norms throughout its history. From the unification of Nepal in 1768 until the transition from the Rana regime to democracy in 1951, Nepal struggled to effectively implement democratic principles. Despite aspirations for advancement, development, and political maturity, establishing a lasting democratic framework has remained a formidable task. A range of factors, including political instability, conflicting ideologies among political parties, external influences, and political system weaknesses, have impeded the smooth operation of democratic processes. (Khanal, 2001) Following the attainment of democracy in 1951, Nepal experienced numerous political fluctuations that strained its democratic foundation. The restoration of democracy in 1991, prompted by a popular uprising, led to the establishment of a constitutional monarchy, a multi-party democratic structure, and the safeguarding of human rights. Nevertheless, this revitalized democratic phase encountered various hurdles. Challenges such as governments struggling to complete their terms, frequent delays in elections, recurring hung parliaments, and ongoing political unrest and shifting alliances all contributed to an environment of governmental instability, sluggish economic growth, and a diminished public trust in the democratic system.

The five-year period of democratic governments in 1991 to 1996 are unable to establish trust between the government and the populace. Despite laying some groundwork for democracy, the governments were incapable to complete their terms and faced numerous movements and protests. The Maoist insurgency, spanning from 1996 to 2006, severely hindered the functioning of democracy in Nepal, resulting in significant loss of life and widespread destruction of infrastructure. (Upreti, 2009) These issues intensified the pre-existing challenges confronting the democratic system. Although Nepal underwent three constitution-making processes in 1991, 2006, and 2015, these changes did not bring about substantial improvements in the country's socio-economic conditions, public confidence in the government, or the investment environment. Political problems, corruption, and external influences persisted. Despite various alterations in political systems, structures, and constitutions, economic conditions for the population did not see significant enhancements. Demographic changes, particularly significant migration, reshaped the population distribution, while the anticipated advancements in education and healthcare systems were not realized. Inequality endured, and development objectives became increasingly unattainable. Many attribute these challenges to issues of governance and the struggles in effectively implementing democracy in Nepal.

Nepal continues to face numerous hurdles in its pursuit of strengthening democratic principles. These obstacles originate from a tumultuous past marked by political instability, persistent economic underdevelopment, an unstable electoral system, and ongoing political conflicts. As a result, the effectiveness of governance has waned, leading to a decrease in public trust in the government. Unfortunately, there has been limited progress in establishing confidence in the external sector. These circumstances prompt us to reflect on the underlying causes of these challenges and the specific obstacles currently confronting Nepal. (Pathak, 2012)

Democracy is a widely accepted political system that places importance on citizen participation in decision-making processes and the protection of individual rights. In a democratic system, power is either directly held by the people or exercised through elected representatives who shape laws and policies. (David,2009) Essential elements of democracy include free and fair elections, respect for human rights, adherence to the rule of law, transparency, and accountability. The majority of people today express a preference for democracy over autocracy or totalitarianism.

Governance, which is closely intertwined with democracy, refers to the frameworks and mechanisms through which decisions are formulated and implemented. Good governance entails the presence of effective and transparent institutions, as well as active citizen participation. It emphasizes the principles of the rule of law, respect for human rights, responsiveness, equity, and inclusivity. Nepal is actively working towards strengthening its democratic foundations and promoting effective governance. However, the country faces numerous obstacles and challenges that impede the progress of its democratic processes.

Nepal, despite its democratic journey spanning over 74 years, still grapples with various challenges in its development. The country's low human development indicators, modest average income, heavy economic dependence, internal instability, and fragile peace and order situation pose significant obstacles. Furthermore, weak government institutions, frequent leadership changes, and other barriers to progress have led to a growing sense of dissatisfaction among the population. Despite strides made in transitioning to a federal democratic republic, these hurdles persist and hinder the consolidation and effectiveness of Nepal's democratic institutions. Given this context, it becomes essential to analyze the major hurdles and challenges faced by Nepal and explore potential solutions to address them.

2. Objectives and Methodology: The primary objective of this study is to thoroughly assess the challenges related to governance and democracy in Nepal, focusing on the ongoing struggle to achieve stability and prosperity despite the country's developmental issues. The research seeks to identify the key barriers hindering effective governance and democracy in Nepal and develop practical recommendations to address these challenges.

By analyzing empirical evidence, reviewing official documents, and consulting experts, the study aims to highlight the existing problems and obstacles faced by the nation. Despite various efforts to address the challenges in Nepali democracy and governance, the outcomes remain a significant question. The methodology employed in this study is a systematic approach that involves planning, conceptualizing, and conducting research. This includes formulating research questions, selecting appropriate research designs, collecting and analyzing data, and drawing valid conclusions. The selection of the research methodology, focusing on the impact of democratic practices and governance challenges in Nepal, is guided by the nature of the study, research questions, and available resources. An analytical methods approach is utilized to break down complex issues, propose solutions, and present formal arguments. Additionally, secondary sources of information have been integrated into the study to enhance the depth of insights and data collection.

3. Review of Literature: The purpose of the literature review in this study is to provide a comprehensive overview and analysis of existing research and theoretical frameworks related to the study of hurdles faced by democracy and governance in Nepal. The literature review aims to synthesize and critically evaluate the key themes, concepts, and theories that are relevant to understanding the challenges encountered in the context of Nepali democracy and governance. The structure of the literature review will be thematically organized, focusing on

narrative discussions that highlight various theoretical perspectives, empirical findings, and scholarly debates related to the obstacles to effective democracy and governance in Nepal. By structuring the literature review thematically, the study aims to provide a coherent and in-depth analysis of the complexities and issues surrounding democratic practices and governance in Nepal. The literature review will serve as a foundation for the study, offering a theoretical framework and contextual background that informs the research questions, methodology, and analysis of the hurdles of democracy and governance in Nepal. By engaging with relevant literature and theories, the study seeks to contribute new insights and perspectives to the ongoing discourse on democratic challenges in Nepal.

The review of existing literature on governance and democracy challenges in Nepal involves a comprehensive analysis aimed at identifying key issues and their impact on the country's political landscape. This complex area of study involves examining scholarly works, government reports, policy documents, and research articles to gain insights into the multifaceted nature of governance and democracy in Nepal. The literature highlights significant hindrances to effective governance, including prolonged underdevelopment, pervasive corruption, weak institutional frameworks, and lack of transparency. Scholars such as Sharma (2018) and Gurung (2019) emphasize the detrimental effects of corruption on public trust, economic development, and the functioning of democratic institutions. Furthermore, the literature underscores the importance of addressing governance challenges through decentralization and citizen engagement (Bhatta, 2020). Consequently, widespread poverty and unemployment in Nepal can contribute to eroding public trust in the government, thus weakening the democratic system. This is evident in Nepal's low economic growth rate of approximately 4% per annum over the past decades, which can be seen as a weakness of the democratic structure. (MoF, 2023)

A comprehensive review of the literature reveals that poverty, unemployment, and low economic development pose significant threats to democracy. Scholars such as Sen (1999) and Acemoglu and Robinson (2012) argue that economic inequality and lack of opportunities can result in political instability and social unrest. The persistent challenges of poverty and unemployment in Nepal hinder citizens' participation in democratic processes and erode trust in the government. Moreover, low economic development can limit the resources available for public services and infrastructure, further impacting the functioning of democratic institutions (Dahal, 2017).

Climate change and disasters also have profound effects on governance and democracy in Nepal. Studies by Bhattarai et al. (2019) and Uprety (2015) highlight how natural disasters, such as floods and earthquakes, can disrupt governmental structures and exacerbate political and social vulnerabilities. The impacts of climate change, including changing weather patterns and resource scarcity, can strain governance systems and necessitate adaptive policies and strategies (Reilly et al., 2014). Such challenges put pressure on democratic processes and decision-making, as governments strive to address immediate humanitarian needs and balance the long-term sustainability of the country.

Furthermore, the literature emphasizes that socio-economic development and democracy are intertwined. Scholars like Przeworski et al. (2000) argue that democracy can foster socio-economic development by promoting the rule of law, protecting human rights, and creating an environment conducive to private sector growth. Conversely, socio-economic development plays a crucial role in sustaining democratic systems by providing stability, enabling citizens' access to basic necessities, and fostering a sense of inclusion and

participation (Gurung, 2019). This interdependence reinforces the need to address poverty, unemployment, and economic development challenges as integral components of strengthening governance and democracy in Nepal.

Writers such as Khadka (2017) and Dahal (2020) argue that the country has faced numerous democratic setbacks, including political polarization, ethnic tensions, and weak democratic institutions. The literature highlights the need for inclusive governance structures and policies that address social inequalities (Poudel, 2016). Additionally, the literature emphasizes the importance of a strong civil society and independent media in promoting democratic values and accountability (Thapa, 2019). The literature also suggests that weak governance and democracy negatively affect public service delivery, economic growth, and social cohesion (Sijapati, 2018). Moreover, scholars argue that these challenges undermine trust in political leaders and institutions, posing a threat to the stability and legitimacy of the government (Basnet, 2017).

The literature emphasizes the importance of tackling various issues to enhance democracy, including economic challenges, corruption, weak public institutions, low economic growth, political instability, polarization, and social inequalities. By addressing these factors, governance can be strengthened, and democratic values can be promoted within the country.

4. Theoretical Concept: When examining the challenges of democracy and governance in Nepal, various significant theoretical concepts can be explored. First and foremost is the theory of democratization and governance, which examines into the processes and mechanisms involved in societies transitioning towards more democratic forms of governance. In Nepal's context, understanding the nation's democratization journey can illuminate the difficulties and barriers encountered in solidifying democratic practices. Governance theory, on the other hand, focuses on the structures, processes, and actors governing a society. By analyzing governance theories, study can scrutinize the establishment and sustainability of effective governance practices in Nepal, despite the prevailing obstacles.

The concept of neopatrimonialism scrutinizes the persistence of patron-client relationships and personalized governance styles that can erode democratic institutions and processes. In Nepal, neo patrimonial practices may hinder the establishment of transparent and accountable governance structures. Meanwhile, the concept of political culture emphasizes the importance of comprehending the prevalent attitudes, values, and beliefs in Nepali society towards democracy and governance. Exploring political culture can shed light on the challenges stemming from cultural aspects that might impede democratic consolidation in Nepal.

Likewise, enquiring into conflict theory is crucial for understanding the impact of historical, social, and political conflicts on democratic governance challenges in Nepal. Conflict theory provides insights into how unresolved tensions and inequalities affect the stability and efficacy of democratic institutions. Theoretical perspectives on development and democracy underscore the interplay between socio-economic advancement and political governance. Exploring development theories can elucidate how economic inequalities, poverty, and resource limitations influence democratic processes in Nepal.

Incorporating theoretical frameworks related to state-building and nation-building help unravel how the cultivation of a unified national identity and efficient state institutions impacts democratic governance in Nepal. By integrating these theoretical concepts into the

research, a deeper analysis of the multifaceted factors and dynamics shaping the country's political landscape can be achieved. This comprehensive approach may offer valuable insights for policymakers, researchers, and practitioners aiming to tackle the obstacles to democratic governance in Nepal.

The philosophical overview on the theme involves examining issues such as power, legitimacy, justice, and ethical responsibilities through the lens of political philosophy. Philosophical thinkers consider concepts such as social contract theory to assess the relationship between the government and its citizens, as well as ethical theories like utilitarianism and virtue ethics to analyze moral dilemmas and ethical considerations in governance practices. By exploring these philosophical perspectives, a deeper understanding of the normative principles, ethical frameworks, and political values shaping Nepal's democratic processes and governance can be gained, offering insights into the structural obstacles and systemic injustices hindering the realization of democratic ideals in the country.

5. Governance and Democratic Principles in Nepal: Democracy serves as a governmental structure where authority is vested in the populace, who exercise it either directly or through elected representatives. This system is underpinned by principles of equality, freedom, and participation, empowering individuals to partake in decision-making and upholding their rights and liberties. Nepal initially adopted a democratic framework in 1951 and progressively enhanced it until the establishment of a democratic constitution in 2015, transitioning the nation into a federal republic.

The democratic system in Nepal is based on the principles of multi-party competition, free and fair elections, and the protection of fundamental rights and freedoms. The Constitution of Nepal guarantees a range of rights and liberties, including the right to vote, freedom of speech, assembly, and expression, and the right to participate in political activities. The democratic structure in Nepal consists of three branches of government: the executive, legislative, and judiciary. The executive branch is headed by the President, who is the ceremonial head of state, and the Prime Minister, who is the head of government. The legislative branch consists of a bicameral parliament, with the House of Representatives (lower house) and the National Assembly (upper house). The judiciary is independent and responsible for interpreting and applying laws.

Democracy in Nepal is practiced through regular elections at national, provincial, and local levels. The country has held several elections since the adoption of the new constitution, including elections for the federal parliament, provincial assemblies, and local bodies. These elections provide Nepali citizens with the opportunity to choose their representatives and shape the direction of the country. However, the practice of democracy in Nepal faces some challenges. Political instability, corruption, and weak institutions are significant obstacles that hinder effective democratic governance. Ensuring inclusivity and representation of marginalized groups, such as women, ethnic minorities, and disadvantaged communities, also remains a challenge.

Nevertheless, efforts are being made to strengthen democracy in Nepal. These include initiatives to promote citizen participation and engagement, enhance transparency and accountability, and strengthen the capacity of democratic institutions. The ongoing process of implementing federalism, along with constitutional provisions promoting social justice and inclusion, aims to ensure democratic governance at all levels. Overall, while there are areas

for improvement, democracy continues to play a crucial role in Nepal's governance system by providing a platform for citizens to exercise their rights, participate in decision-making, and hold their elected representatives accountable.

Governance refers to the processes and systems through which public decisions are made, resources are allocated, and authority is exercised in a society. It encompasses the structures, institutions, and mechanisms that shape and guide government actions, policies, and programs. In Nepal, governance is practiced through a democratic system that is enshrined in the Constitution of Nepal. The governance structure in Nepal is based on the principles of federalism, separation of powers, and decentralization. The country is divided into seven provinces, each with its own provincial government, and local units known as municipalities and rural municipalities.

At the national level, governance in Nepal is carried out through three branches of government - the executive, legislative, and judiciary. The executive branch consists of the President, the Prime Minister, and the Council of Ministers. The legislative branch is composed of the federal parliament consisting of two houses: the House of Representatives (lower house) and the National Assembly (upper house). The judiciary is responsible for interpreting and applying laws, ensuring the rule of law, and protecting citizens' rights. The governance structure also includes various independent constitutional bodies and commissions that oversee specific sectors, such as the Election Commission, the Commission for the Investigation of Abuse of Authority, and the National Human Rights Commission. These bodies act as checks and balances on the government and play a crucial role in ensuring good governance.

5.1 World Governance Indicator: The World Governance Indicators (WGI) are a set of aggregate indexes produced by the World Bank that measure the quality of governance in countries worldwide, evaluating six dimensions: voice and accountability, political stability and absence of violence, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law, and control of corruption. (Kaufman,2010) These indicators draw from various data sources, including surveys and expert assessments, to offer a comprehensive assessment of governance performance globally. Utilized by policymakers, researchers, and the public, the WGI framework provides valuable insights into the state of governance, revealing trends and progress in areas such as citizen engagement, political stability, and combating corruption. In the case of Nepal, recent data indicates slight advancements in certain dimensions of governance, with progress in Voice and Accountability showcasing increased citizen engagement and freedom of expression, while challenges persist regarding Political Stability and Absence of Violence, reflecting the country's transition from conflict to a more stable political environment.

Table 1**World Governance indicators and Nepal**

year	Theme	VA	PSAV	GE	RQ	RL	CC	Average
2020	Band Score	15.94	28.30	24.76	26.19	20.95	20.0	22.69
	Rank	42.51	41.51	15.71	25.71	32.38	29.05	31.1
2021	Band Score	15.46	25.0	24.76	21.90	21.90	23.81	21.91
	Rank	43.00	41.04	15.71	28.57	33.81	32.38	32.4
2022	Band Score	15.46	26.89	24.04	21.23	21.23	25.0	23.02
	Rank	44.93	37.73	16.04	27.83	37.74	33.96	33.0

Source: www.worldbank.org.

Note: The six dimensions of governance assessed by the World Bank's World Governance Indicators (WGI) are: 1. Voice and Accountability (VA), 2. Political Stability and Absence of Violence (PSAV), 3. Government Effectiveness (GE), 4. Regulatory Quality (RQ), 5. Rule of Law (RL), 6. Control of Corruption (CC).

The table above highlights Nepal's average governance scores and ranks across various dimensions for the years 2020, 2021, and 2022. The average scores were 22.69 (ranked at 31.145), 21.91 (ranked at 32.418), and 23.02 (ranked at 33.038) respectively. These figures indicate that Nepal's overall governance performance, as evaluated by the World Governance Indicators, has shown not significant progress. Though, there has been some fluctuation in the scores, they have mostly stayed within a moderate range. In terms of all individual dimensions like voice and accountability, political stability, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law, and control of corruption, Nepal's ranks are below average. This suggests that Nepal's governance pattern has not made substantial progresses in recent years.

Table 2**Some Economic Development Indicators of Nepal in 2022**

S No	Indicators	Unit	Score	Rank World-wide
1	Size of Economy (GDP), 2022	Billion US Dollar	40.83	96/177
2	Population, (National Census 2021)	Million	29.3	49/234
3	Per capita GDP, 2022	US Dollar	1337	161/190
4	Economic Growth rate, 2022	Percent	4.2	-
5	Share of Agriculture in GDP, 2022	Percent	23.95	27/164
6	Absolute Poverty level, 2022	Percent	15.1	65/159
7	Human Development Index (HDI), 2022	point	0.601	146/193
8	Corruption Perception Index, 2022	score	35	108/180
9	Total Public Debt, 2022	Billion US Dollar	15.36	113/210
10	Literacy rate 6+ years	Percent	76.3	180/207
11	Life expectancy at birth	year	71.4	137/201

Source: World Bank data, Worldometer, Economic Survey 2079/80 (2022/23), National Census 2021 .

The information provided in the table above presents key indicators that shed light on Nepal's politico-economic landscape in 2022. It outlines Nepal's GDP size of \$40.83 billion, ranking 96th out of 177 countries globally, and a per capita GDP of \$1337, ranking 161st among 190 countries. The population of Nepal is 29.3 million, making it the 49th largest in the world, with an average economic growth rate of 4.2%. The agriculture sector contributes 23.9% to the GDP, positioning Nepal at 27th from the bottom among 164 countries, with an absolute poverty level of 15.1%. Nepal's Human Development Index (HDI) in 2022 is 0.601, placing it at the 146th position among 193 countries. The total public debt, encompassing domestic and external debt, amounts to \$15.36 billion. Furthermore, the literacy rate for individuals aged 6 and above is 76.3%, ranking 180th among 207 countries in the world, while the average life expectancy at birth is 71.4 years, positioning Nepal at 137th among 201 countries. These indicators collectively depict various facets of Nepal's challenging economy, encompassing size, growth, sectoral contributions, poverty levels, human development, and fiscal condition, reflecting the country's complex development status. Nepal's comparative indicators suggest that the country is underdeveloped and lagging behind. The rankings across different measures highlight the challenges faced and underscore the imperative need for enhancements in various developmental sectors.

5.2 The least development status in five decades: The classification known as the Least Developed Countries (LDC) category has been used by the United Nations for the past five decades to identify countries that confront severe socio-economic challenges, such as extreme poverty, low human development, and vulnerability to external shocks. Introduced in 1971, this categorization aims to address the unique needs of the world's poorest and most marginalized countries. To transition out of the LDC category, a country must fulfill specific criteria outlined by the United Nations related to income, human assets, and economic vulnerability, and maintain these requirements for a minimum of two consecutive triennial reviews. The decision to graduate is ultimately made by the United Nations General Assembly, following recommendations from the United Nations Economic and Social Council. Currently, there are 46 countries designated as LDCs, with Nepal being one of them since 1971. For graduation, the specific threshold values established by the United Nations include a GNI per capita of \$1,306 or higher, a Human Assets Index (HAI) score of at least 66 out of 100, and an Economic Vulnerability Index (EVI) score no more than 32 out of 100. Nepal has achieved favorable scores in the indicators except GNI per capita, demonstrating progress towards graduation.

Table 3

Graduation Thresholds: 2024 Triennial Review

Particulars	Gross National Income (GNI) per capita	Human Assets Index (HAI)	Economic Vulnerability Index (EVI)
Graduation Thresholds	GNI per capita: \$1,306 or above (Income-only: \$3,918 or above)	66 or above	32 or below
Nepal's Status	\$1300	76.3	29.7

Source: <https://www.un.org/development/desa/dpad/least-developed-country-category/ldc-graduation.html>

Nepal has met all three criteria required for its Least Developed Country (LDC) Graduation threshold, indicating a satisfactory progression. The country aims to transition from the least developed category to the developing nation status by 2026. Despite achieving this significant milestone, Nepal faces numerous obstacles in maintaining this graduation, ensuring continuance, and accelerating its development progress towards becoming a developed country.

6. Discussion on the Hurdles of Democracy and Governance: Despite efforts to promote stability and prosperity, Nepal confronts various hurdles that impede progress towards effective governance and a democratic society, obstructing its path to development. Overcoming these obstacles requires the implementation of strategies such as identifying challenges, acquiring resources, developing plans, and promoting adaptability, underscoring the importance of cooperation and open-mindedness. Governance challenges in Nepal, including corruption, political instability, weak institutions, and limited citizen participation, are being tackled through anti-corruption measures, transparency initiatives, and citizen engagement programs like local elections and social inclusion efforts. Recent measures to bolster governance include the establishment of feedback mechanisms, such as the grievance redressal system and the Right to Information Act, aimed at enhancing transparency, accountability, and citizen engagement. Based on a literature review, the accompanying table offers insights into Nepal's governance practices and socio-economic status.

Figure 1

An Overview of Hurdles of Governance and Democracy in Nepal

Source: synthesized by reviewing the literature.

6.1 Political Uncertainty in Nepal: Nepal has faced with recurring of political instability marked by frequent shifts in governmental structures. The nation underwent a significant

evolution from a monarchy to a federal democratic republic, initiating a complex governance process. Over the past three decades, spanning from 1990 to 2022, Nepal has experienced a considerable turnover, witnessing the formation of as many as 29 different governments. This ongoing flux has given rise to challenges such as inconsistent policies, compromised governance, the commercialization of politics, slow economic development, and a decline in public trust. These repercussions significantly impact the robustness of the democratic framework in the country.

The rapid succession of governments has resulted in policy inconsistencies, hindering the formulation and implementation of long-term strategies. Furthermore, the unpredictable nature of political alliances and coalitions has led to weakened governance structures, impeding the effectiveness of administrative processes. The frequent changes in leadership have, at times, fostered a perception of politics as a profitable enterprise, shifting attention from public welfare to personal gains. The prevalent trend of individuals entering politics solely for economic gains often results in politicians being granted privileges rather than facing legal penalties. This pattern contributes to an environment where economic development is sidelined, diverting focus from sustainable growth strategies. As a result, people either lose faith in their government or aspire to seek a better future abroad.

6.2 Constitutional alterations: Over a span of seventy-five years, Nepal has witnessed the creation of seven constitutions, each aiming to shape a more modern, developed, and just citizenry. These constitutions articulate alluring yet sometimes unattainable aspirations. However, the actualization of the constitution remains elusive, with issues surrounding its drafting and implementation proving contentious. Matters pertaining to federalism, representation, and the rights of diverse ethnic and social groups have been persistent sources of tension. Certain groups feel marginalized by the constitution and advocate for greater inclusion and recognition.

While the current constitution has enshrined various rights, such as the right to shelter, employment, food security, education, and health, practical access to these rights remains limited for many. Despite the existence of over a dozen constitutional bodies and commissions aimed at addressing the needs of underprivileged people, the status of these groups has seen little improvement. It's evident that merely amending the constitution may not be the ultimate solution to these challenges.

6.3 Socio-ethnic Struggles: Nepal exhibits a vibrant mosaic of population diversity, embracing a multitude of ethnicities, languages, and cultures. Steering through the democratic terrain to ensure fair representation for diverse groups presents a substantial challenge. Concerns surrounding identity, autonomy, and self-governance surface as contentious issues in nations like Nepal, with the potential to spark conflicts. Finding common ground among the various groups proves to be a daunting task, as evidenced by the intricacies encountered in establishing provincial structures within the federal setup in Nepal. Effectively managing ethnic and communal tensions becomes crucial, posing challenges to the stability of democracy.

6.4 Economic Challenges and Democracy: Nepal's democratic structure confronts a pressing challenge in the form of economic sluggishness. Despite embracing a democratic regime in 1951 and reaffirming it in 1991, the nation's economic markers fall behind those of its peers. Progress in terms of livelihood and economic conditions has been minimal, with 15.1% of the population still below the poverty line. Nepal's Human Development Index (HDI) modestly stands at 0.602, and the average economic growth remains below five percent. A negative trade balance amplifies economic dependency, and foreign direct investment (FDI) has fallen short of expectations, leaving per capita income at a \$1,399.

Remittances, constituting about one-fourth of its GDP, merely serve as a measure to counterbalance the negative trade situation. These sluggish economic developments present formidable challenges that impact the overall stability of the democratic system, underscoring the urgent need to address economic issues and foster inclusive growth for the success of democracy.

Nepal must confront its economic challenges comprehensively to fortify its democratic foundations. Prioritizing initiatives that enhance livelihoods, expand employment opportunities, promote self-sufficiency over dependency, alleviate poverty, and achieve robust and sustainable economic growth is paramount for democratic governance. A crucial component of this endeavor is the imperative for political will and commitment to economic development, which is vital for averting economic decline and safeguarding democracy from impending threats.

6.5 Corruption's Impact on Democracy: Nepal faces with persistent concerns about corruption, which can significantly challenge democratic institutions and processes. Democracy inherently relies on accountability and responsibility; without these pillars, democratic integrity falters, and corruption can thrive. Unfortunately, efforts to fortify policies, legislation, and institutions to combat corruption appear inadequate. Recent years have witnessed high-profile scandals, such as the Lalita Nibas public land scam, Ncell tax evasion, Wide-body aircraft procurement deal, gold smuggling, and irregularities in IT equipment purchases. Transparency International's study places Nepal at a concerning 108th rank out of 180 countries in terms of good governance, securing only 35 out of 100 indicators. The extent of corruption is evident in the staggering number of nearly 28,000 corruption-related complaints registered, with 162 cases filed in the special court against corruption by the CIAA in the 2021/22 fiscal year. These cases primarily involve charges of bribery, document forgery, abuse of public authority, illegal benefits, and revenue embezzlement. The Auditor General's office identified irregular expenses or transaction in its 60th report amounting to 119.7 billion Nrs out of the audited 7139 billion Nrs in the fiscal year 2021/22 alone. Such misuse of public funds and the deterioration of public discipline not only compromise democratic norms and values but also erode public trust in the government, impeding the effective functioning of democratic principles.

6.6 Geo-Political Security and Environmental Challenges in Nepal: The nation faces with a range of issues, including climate change vulnerability, natural disasters, and security concerns, all of which pose substantial threats to the democratic system. Nepal is particularly vulnerable to various natural adversities such as earthquakes, pandemics, droughts, and floods, resulting in the displacement of human settlements and potential long-term threats to democracy. Coping with the aftermath of these disasters' burdens governmental resources, creating obstacles for democratic governance. Persistent historical conflicts, exemplified by the decade-long Maoist political struggles, Terai-Madhesh conflicts, and numerous other recurring agitations and movements, contribute to enduring security challenges.

Nepal faces geopolitical pressure, contending with external relations characterized by power politics, hegemony, influences, and a struggle for existence. Powerful nations with significant economic, political, and geographical interests engage in complex interactions, and these dynamics can potentially hinder democratic processes in Nepal. Therefore, it is crucial to prioritize the maintenance of peace and address security concerns to ensure the steadfastness of democratic institutions.

Obstacles to the democratic system have the potential to create bottleneck in political processes, hindering the passage of legislation and the resolution of crucial issues. This hindrance can weaken the government's capacity to operate effectively. Simultaneously, the

possibility of political instability and public discontent may lead to social unrest and protests. Public dissatisfaction with government actions or performance may manifest through public demonstrations and strikes. The economic impact of political instability can be substantial, deterring foreign investment and obstructing overall economic growth. Governments facing instability may encounter challenges in implementing necessary economic reforms.

During periods of political unrest, concerns may emerge regarding the protection of human rights, posing challenges to safeguarding the rights of both citizens and minority groups. Additionally, instability can have repercussions on Nepal's international relations, as frequent changes in leadership and governmental policies may affect diplomatic ties and international collaboration. As Nepal confronts multifaceted challenges on its democratic journey, it is important addressing these issues to fortify and sustain the democratic system of the nation. This will contribute to fostering a resilient and inclusive political landscape for the future.

7. Conclusion: After reviewing relevant literature, analyzing indicators, and giving thoughtful consideration, several key conclusions have been drawn to tackle the governance and democracy challenges in Nepal. These conclusions are based on a thorough understanding of the issues and are designed to enhance the country's governance and democratic systems. These findings are anticipated to be beneficial for researchers, policymakers, and stakeholders engaged in addressing these challenges.

7.1. Political stability: Achieving political stability and effectively implementing the constitution is crucial for Nepal. Certain provisions, such as the high proportion of an indirect election system and the early termination of the executive head, along with the political influence on the formation of constitutional bodies, can be amended to improve the situation. Encouraging political parties and leaders to engage in constructive dialogue, prioritize national interest over personal or party interests, and foster inclusive decision-making processes are essential to address political polarization and ethnic tensions (Dahal, 2020). Additionally, it is recommended to encourage local governing bodies to adopt fair and responsive governance styles, promoting sustainable democratic processes. To prevent the misuse of resources at the provincial and local levels, it is equally important to establish a constitutional body for oversight and control.

7.2. Strengthening good governance: Strengthening good governance is essential in Nepal, as deep-rooted corruption undermines democracy and weakens the democratic culture. To uphold democratic values, it is necessary to promote a fair and transparent environment in public activities. This can be achieved by implementing robust anti-corruption measures, including the establishment of norms, values and specialized agencies, promoting transparency and accountability, and imposing strict penalties for corrupt practices. By taking these actions, pervasive corruption can be addressed, restoring public trust in the governance system (Sharma, 2018). Enhancing Institutional Capacity involves Improving the capacity and functioning of government institutions through training programs, institutional reforms, and effective management practices. This will contribute to more efficient and effective governance (Gurung, 2019). Building strong democratic institutions, such as independent judiciary, electoral bodies, and human rights commissions, to ensure the rule of law, protect human rights, and foster democratic values (Khadka, 2017)

7.3. Socio-Economic development: Nepal continues to grapple with a multitude of economic challenges that have a direct impact on its democracy and governance. These challenges include widespread poverty, high unemployment rates, and a relatively low GDP. Additionally, the country faces trade deficits, economic dependency, limited resources, and a

heavy debt burden. The result of these challenges is evident as nearly five million Nepalis seek job opportunities abroad. In order to strengthen democracy and governance in Nepal, these economic issues must be addressed effectively. By focusing on economic growth, generating employment opportunities, reducing poverty, and promoting sustainable development, the country can alleviate the significant strain on its democracy and governance system (Shrestha, 2020).

7.4. Addressing Infrastructure development and Social Inequalities: Nepal is confronted with numerous challenges in infrastructure development, particularly in sectors such as education, transportation, communication, and electricity. It is essential to address these infrastructure gaps in order to sustain democracy and build trust in the government. By investing in infrastructure and providing equal opportunities, the government can build confidence among citizens and encourage them to stay in their respective communities. Moreover, it is crucial to design and implement policies and programs that specifically target social inequalities, including disparities based on ethnicity, caste, and gender. This approach will foster inclusive governance and promote social cohesion, effectively strengthening democracy and governance in Nepal (Poudel, 2016).

The longstanding challenges faced by democracy and governance in Nepal have significantly impacted the well-being of its people, hindering global development progress and eroding public trust in government institutions. Addressing these issues requires a united effort to reinforce democratic principles, essential for a stable governance framework. Collaboration among policymakers, researchers, and governance professionals is essential to devise a comprehensive strategy to overcome barriers and advance governance practices and democratic ideals in Nepal. This collective action is key to shaping a promising future by promoting transparency, accountability, and inclusivity in governance systems.

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